

Question raised by requestor

1. Is there any Register of certificates confirming that the relevant persons have competence in the field of animal welfare? If such a register exists, could you please provide:
 - a. link to any of it (to see the information it contains);
 - b. information on procedures for management (maintain) of such register.
2. Who has the right to conduct animal welfare compliance training? What are they: the legal entities or persons? Can educational institutions, associations of producers, a competent authority do this?
3. What is a Procedure for authorizing relevant legal entities to carry out training on compliance with animal welfare legislation? What criteria must be met to be authorized to carry out such training? Is it possible to get such legal act on national level on procedure of authorization (or web link to it)?
4. Is there a list of approved topics (programs) for the training of persons whose duties include keeping, killing, transportation of animals and/or carrying out related operations? Could you share such a list for our review?
5. How knowledge and skills are tested after training on animal welfare legislation? Are these tests paper-based or computer-based? Is it an exam and if yes - written/oral? Is there a practical skills test (e.g., killing of animals or related operations) before certification?
6. Duration of animal welfare training courses (in hours or weeks)?
7. Is there any procedure for issuing a certificate of completion of training on animal welfare legislation (maybe you may share any link to national legislation)?
8. Are there any approved Forms of documents that must be submitted to obtain a certificate (application, declaration/ a statement that the person was not brought to justice, possibly other forms)?
9. Is the form of the certificate of completion of training in accordance with the requirements of animal welfare legislation approved? Is it possible for us to see how such a certificate looks like?
10. Is any temporary admission forms approved? Is it possible for us to see how it looks like?

Answer

- 1 Is there any Register of certificates confirming that the relevant persons have competence in the field of animal welfare? If such a register exists, could you please provide:**
 - 1.a link to any of it (to see the information it contains);*
 - 1.b information on procedures for management (maintain) of such register.*

Answer:

No available information.

- 2 Who has the right to conduct animal welfare compliance training? What are they: the legal entities or persons? Can educational institutions, associations of producers, a competent authority do this?**

Answer:

National legislative provisions regarding the prevention of cruelty and unnecessary suffering of animals were first developed in England in 1911, after which many other EU countries followed, such as Denmark in 1916, Germany in 1933, Norway in 1935 and Sweden in 1944. Stakeholders within the livestock production chain (farmers, transport personnel, official inspectors, etc.) are obliged to comply with European and National legislation and regulatory instructions. General principles for the protection of animals kept for farming purposes are described in the EU Council Directive 98/58/EC. Protection of animals at the time of killing is established through Council Regulation 1099/2009/EC. Furthermore, the welfare of animals during transport is regulated by Council Regulation No 1/2005 on the protection of animals during transport and related operations.

Although the above regulations are directly applicable across the European Union and European Commission is responsible for monitoring the implementation of EU legislative requirements, there is no formal training in the EU to certify that farmers are familiar to animal-based welfare indicators or best welfare practices.

Among EU countries, Portugal, Spain and Slovenia require in law that ruminants or equines caretakers have to be trained in animal welfare. Other countries like France, Finland, Poland, Czech Republic, Ireland, Netherlands and Germany also have legal requirements for training but only for other species such as poultry and/or pigs. To be noted that France requires an animal welfare representative (e.g. the owner, a caretaker) on all farms (including ruminants and equines farms) and any person keeping at least one equine for professional or personal reasons must have a diploma or experience as defined in law. For more details on countries requiring training for other species only, we suggest to contact the related National Competent Authorities or the other EURCAWs.

In general, the training courses are conducted by public or private entities approved by the National Competent Authority. The procedure for authorising those entities to conduct courses is sometimes described in law (e.g. Article 5 of Order no. 9485/2015 in Portugal legislation). The trainers must have a sufficient qualification and appropriate experience in animal welfare to give the training courses.

Voluntary training courses at European and national level:

The European Union Reference Centers for Animal Welfare (EURCAWs) give free access to training material (templates, quality standards, guides, recommendations and technical support) used in other countries for training and continuing education of inspectors, targeted towards prioritised welfare areas along the value chain (on-farm, transport, slaughter). A certificate of competence is not applicable, but the material can be used to set preliminary recommendations for training at national level. Furthermore, EURCAW Ruminants & Equines has developed and piloted a web-based Training Needs Analysis (TNA), to design the long-term training strategy for the Centre. The TNA aims to identify knowledge and skills gaps that prevent the Member States' Competent Authorities, policy workers and their Support Bodies from effectively performing and excelling in their roles as regards the welfare of ruminants and equines. A Training Needs Analysis Platform (TraNAP) has been developed to facilitate data collection and reporting of the TNA. It represents a permanent and centralised environment where the TNA will be carried out periodically.

Target group: Competent Authorities

Formal training that officially certifies the competence on animal welfare is provided by BTSF Academy (Better Training for Safer Food) and is addressed to official veterinarians and other personnel conducting animal welfare control. BTSF is a European Commission training initiative to improve the knowledge and implementation of EU rules covering food safety, animal health and welfare, and the One Health concept. Training delivery is usually conducted by external contractors through workshops, webinars or sustained training missions in groups of 15-40 people from one country, regional grouping of countries or third countries.

Target group: Animal Transporters

The 4-day course "Enforcement of animal welfare during transport" is aimed to provide EU Member States and neighbouring non-EU countries with high-level effective training to ensure better organisation, uniform implementation and effective enforcement of the EU rules on the welfare of animals during transport. Competent authorities, transport companies and local NGOs can apply for the course. Authorisation certificates are issued by National Competent Authorities. The training for drivers and attendants includes:

- principles for animal welfare and fitness for transport
- appropriate handling, loading and unloading to prevent injuries and minimise stress
- indication of space allowance per animal
- inspection of facilities to ensure the optimal microclimatic and environmental conditions
- guidelines for resting periods, watering and feeding during the journey

Moreover, vocational training programmes focusing on animal welfare are provided by private organisations and companies, such as following:

- Teagasc (Agriculture and Food Development Authority, <https://www.teagasc.ie/food/research-and-innovation/research-areas/food-industry-development/specialist-training/certificate-of-competence-in-animal-welfare/>),

In addition, the website <https://disa.slu.se> (the English pages currently under reconstruction) provides materials on biological principles and slaughter of animals. The material is an Open Educational Resource free to use.

3 What is a Procedure for authorizing relevant legal entities to carry out training on compliance with animal welfare legislation? What criteria must be met to be authorized to carry out such training? Is it possible to get such legal act on national level on procedure of authorization (or web link to it)?

Answer:

Training may be provided by governmental or private bodies.

4 Is there a list of approved topics (programs) for the training of persons whose duties include keeping, killing, transportation of animals and/or carrying out related operations? Could you share such a list for our review?

Answer:

The training topics are detailed in law and some examples of the main categories for mandatory training sessions are provided below:

- **Portugal** (for ruminants and equines): animal welfare and stress concepts, animal physiology, animal behaviour, caretakers behaviour, equipments, legislative requirements, transport, consumer behaviour, security of working conditions. Legislative references: Order no. 9485/2015 (Despacho n.º 9485/2015), specific regulation no.9 (regulamento específico n.º 9) of DGAV.
- **Spain** (for bovines): characteristics of bovine production, animal health, hygiene and biosecurity, handling, environmental management and the fight against climate change on farms, registration of information and documentation, regulations at European, national regional and local levels. Legislative references: Royal Decree 1053/2022 of 27 December establishing basic rules for the management of bovine farms (Real Decreto 1053/2022, de 27 de diciembre, por el que se establecen normas básicas de ordenación de las granjas bovinas), Royal Decree 804/2011 of 10 June 2011 regulating the zootechnical, health and animal welfare management of equine holdings and establishing the equine health plan (Real Decreto 804/2011, de 10 de junio, por el que se regula la ordenación zootécnica, sanitaria y de bienestar animal de las explotaciones equinas y se establece el plan sanitario equino).
- **Slovenia** (for all species): detailed training programmes on animal husbandry (Article 14 of Livestock Farming Act), but no training programme on animal needs yet (Animal Protection Act). Legislative references: Article 14 of Livestock Farming Act (Zakon o živinoreji), Regulations on training and professional development in the field of animal husbandry (Pravilnik o usposabljanju in strokovnem izpopolnjevanju na področju živinoreje), Animal Protection Act (Zakon o zaščiti živali).
- **France** (general session common to all species – pigs and poultry for now): animal welfare definition (including the Five Freedoms, emotions, animal needs), legislative requirements on animal protection, societal aspects on animal protection, animal welfare indicators, handling, one welfare concept. Legislative references: Article R214-17 of the rural and maritime fishing code (Article R214-17 du code rural et de la pêche maritime), order of 16 December 2021 defining the procedures for appointing "animal welfare" representatives in all livestock farms and the obligation and conditions for training in animal welfare for persons appointed as representatives in pig or poultry farms (Arrêté du 16 décembre 2021 définissant les modalités de désignation des référents « bien-être animal » dans tous les élevages et l'obligation et les conditions de formation au

bien-être animal des personnes désignées référentes dans les élevages de porcs ou de volailles), Articles L211-10-1 and D214-37-1 of the rural and maritime fishing code (Articles L211-10-1 et D214-37-1 du code rural et de la pêche maritime) for the requirements regarding the keeping of Equidae.

5 How knowledge and skills are tested after training on animal welfare legislation? Are these tests paper-based or computer-based? Is it an exam and if yes - written/oral? Is there a practical skills test (e.g., killing of animals or related operations) before certification?

Answer:

To our knowledge, the knowledge and skills after training are tested only in the case of Portugal for ruminants and equines. However, the training must be renewed after 5 years in Spain (at least 10 hours duration), 7 years in France (all the training, i.e. at least 9 hours duration), and 10 years in Slovenia to comply with the updated knowledge on animal health and welfare.

6 Duration of animal welfare training courses (in hours or weeks)?

Answer:

The modality and duration of the training courses are variable across countries. For example:

- **Portugal:** Farmers with livestock holdings and keepers (with a minimum compulsory education) must follow a training course, established by species or group of species (ruminants and equines (25 hours – see below), pigs, poultry, laying hens, rabbits). They can also follow a supplementary training course (6 hours), complementary to the previous ones. After the training courses, trainees must pass an individual knowledge assessment test in front of a jury. Professionals can ask to the Competent Authority for recognition of equivalence of previously acquired training and professional experience if they can provide appropriate documents.
- **Spain:** On bovine farms (with more than 20 animals), the owner of the farm must designate a person (owner or keeper of bovines) responsible for biosecurity, hygiene, animal health and welfare. All people working with cattle must have adequate training, which consist of a minimum duration of 20 hours on the subjects listed within 6 months of the commencement of their work in the holding, except if they can justify at least 3 years of experience in cattle farming or if they are in possession of one of the 2 diploma listed in law. Regarding equines, there is a requirement for training in animal welfare, but with no content or minimum hours specified for the training courses.
- **Slovenia:** animal handlers must be qualified with appropriate training and knowledge about e.g. breeding, handling, health care, feeding of animals. Several training programs are provided in law depending on the tasks of the handler, but without any details on animal welfare. However, people who take care of farm animals while performing economic activities related to animals must acquire basic knowledge on animals' needs. This can be achieved by possessing a diploma from a list defined in law, or by attending learning courses with an official program and approved providers. The content and duration of this training program is not yet adopted.
- **France:** a person must be designated as the animal welfare representative in all farms. This person must have a diploma from a list in law to be designated as an animal welfare representative. For now, all welfare representatives of farms raising poultry and pigs must complete a training course on animal welfare. It is composed of one common session (2 hours online with topics defined in law, see below) and at least one supplementary session to be chosen by the welfare representative (with at least 7 hours dedicated to animal welfare). The training courses are proposed by the entities designated by the Competent Authority and can be controlled regarding the content of the courses they provide. The 2 minimum sessions must be done within 18 months. Moreover, people working with equines must demonstrate their knowledge on equines needs, by providing proof of a diploma from an established list, or professional experience of at least 18 months.

7 Is there any procedure for issuing a certificate of completion of training on animal welfare legislation (maybe you may share any link to national legislation)?

Answer:

No available information.

8 Are there any approved Forms of documents that must be submitted to obtain a certificate (application, declaration/ a statement that the person was not brought to justice, possibly other forms)?

Answer:

Procedures depend on national laws. References to legislative texts are provided above.

9 Is the form of the certificate of completion of training in accordance with the requirements of animal welfare legislation approved? Is it possible for us to see how such a certificate looks like?

Answer:

No available information.

10 Is any temporary admission forms approved? Is it possible for us to see how it looks like?

Answer:

We have no such information. Please contact the corresponding competent authorities for more details.

References

1. Lundmark, F., Berg, C., Schmid, O., Behdadi, D. & Röcklinsberg, H. 2014. Intentions and Values in Animal Welfare Legislation and Standards. *J Agric Environ Ethics* **27**, 991–1017. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10806-014-9512-0> .
2. EU Council Directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31998L0058> .
3. EU Council Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009 on the protection of animals at the time of killing. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ%3AL%3A2009%3A303%3A0001%3A0030%3AEN%3APDF> .
4. EU Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 on the protection of animals during transport and related operations and amending Directives 64/432/EEC and 93/119/EC and Regulation (EC) No 1255/97. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32005R0001> .
5. European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare-Pigs. <https://eurcaw-pigs.eu/training>
6. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/230138/Dr%20M.Martin_handbook_certification_verkleinert_EN.pdf
7. BTSF Academy-course information. <https://better-training-for-safer-food.ec.europa.eu/training/course/info.php?id=368>

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